

SINGULARYAR Koeffitsientga ega bo'lgan giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi.

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Ko'rinishi o'zgartirilgan Koshi masalasining qo'yilishi.

Annotatsiya: Koshi masalasi qo'yilishi, soha tushunchasi, funktsiya tushunchasi,

Kalif so'zlar: Eyley-Darbu tenglamasi, Koshi masalasi, Beta funktsiyasi, Gamma funktsiyasi.

Ushbu

$$AB = \{(x, y) : 0 < x < 1, y = 0\},$$

$$AC = \{(x, y) : 0 < x < 1/2, x + y = 0\},$$

$$BC = \{(x, y) : 1/2 < x < 1, x - y = 1\}$$

to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan Ω sohada

$$u_{xx} - u_{yy} - \frac{2\beta}{y}u_y = 0, \quad 0 < \beta < 1/2, \quad (1)$$

tenglamaning

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= \tau(x) \\ \lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^{2\beta} u_y(x, y) &= \nu(x) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, y)$ yechimini topish talab etilgan bo'lsin.

Ω sohada (1) tenglamaning koeffitsientlari orasida $a_{12}^2 - a_{11}a_{22} > 0$ ($a_{11} = 1, a_{12} = 0, a_{22} = -1$) munosabat o'rinli bo'lganligi uchun, bu tenglamani shu sohada giperbolik tipga tegishli deyiladi.

AC va BC chiziqlar (1) tenglamaning xarakteristikalarini deyiladi. AB to'g'ri chiziq esa (1) tenglama uchun singulyarlik chizig'i hisoblanadi.

Odatda Koshi masalasining qo'yilishida qaralayotgan sohaning bir qismida qidirilayotgan funksiyaning qiymati va shu qismda qidirilayotgan funksiyaning hosilasi berilib, tenglamaning shu sohada qanoatlantiruvchi funksiyani topishdan iborat bo'lar edi.

Biz qaralayotgan masalada esa (2) shartlardan ikkinchisida funksiya hosilasi oldida vazn funksiyasi qatnashganligi hisobiga, bunday masala ko'rinishi o'zgartirilgan Koshi masalasi deb nom oldi.

Masalani yechilishi.

Avvalo (1)-(2) masalani analitik usulda yechamiz. Buning uchun (1) tenglamaning xarakteristikalarini topishimizga to'g'ri keladi, ya'ni:

$$a_{11}dy^2 - 2a_{12}dxdy + a_{22}dx^2 = 0.$$

Bu yerda $a_{11} = 1, a_{12} = 0, a_{22} = -1$ bo'lganligi uchun, tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi:

$$(dy - dx)(dy + dx) = 0 \text{ yoki } (dx - dy)(dx + dy) = 0.$$

Bundan ko'rinadiki, $x + y = C_1, x - y = C_2$ xarakteristikalar oilasi paydo bo'ladi.

Mos holda bularni ξ va η orqali belgilaymiz, yahni $\xi = x + y$ va $\eta = x - y$.

Aynan shular (1) tenglamaning xarakteristikalarini deyiladi.

Kanonik ko'rinishga o'tish formulalaridan foydalangan holda, quyidagilarni hisoblab

$$\xi_x = 1, \eta_x = 1, \xi_{xx} = 0, \eta_{xx} = 0,$$

$$\xi_y = 1, \eta_y = 1, \xi_{yy} = 0, \eta_{yy} = 0$$

x, y bo'yicha olingan xususiy hosilalarni ξ, η bo'yicha olingan hosilalarga almashtiramiz

$$u_y = u_\xi - u_\eta; \quad u_{xx} = u_{\xi\xi} + 2u_{\xi\eta} + u_{\eta\eta};$$

$$u_{yy} = u_{\xi\xi} - 2u_{\xi\eta} + u_{\eta\eta}.$$

Bu hisob-kitoblarni olib borib, (1) tenglamaga qo'yamiz. U holda (1) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishdagi Eyler-Darbu tenglamasiga keladi [3]:

$$u_{\xi\eta} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi}(u_\eta - u_\xi) = 0. \quad (3)$$

(3) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi mavjud [3] va u quyidagi ko'rinishda:

$$u(\xi, \eta) = (\eta - \xi)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 Z(z) [t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt + \int_0^1 F(z) [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt, \quad (*)$$

bu yerda $z = \xi + (\eta - \xi)t$, $Z, F \in C^2$ – uzluksiz funksiyalar. Eski x va y koordinatalar sistemasiga qaytib, (1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini hosil qilamiz:

$$u(x, y) = (-2y)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 Z(z) [t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt + \int_0^1 F(z) [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt, \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $z = x + y - 2yt$.

Ko'rish qiyin emaski, $F(x)$ funksiyani (4) dan (2) ning birinchi shartidan foydalangan holda topsa bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$u(x, 0) = F(x) \int_0^1 [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt = \tau(x). \quad (5)$$

Oxirgi ifodadagi integral, Beta funksiyaning [2] integral ko'rinishi deb ataladi. Uning Gamma funksiyalar orqali ifodisi quyidagicha:

$$\int_0^1 [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt = B(\beta, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma(\beta)\Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma(\beta + \beta)} = \frac{\Gamma^2(\beta)}{\Gamma(2\beta)}.$$

Oxirgi tenglikdan foydalanib, (5) dan $F(x)$ funksiyaning ko'rinishini yozamiz:

$$F(x) = \frac{\Gamma(2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(\beta)} \tau(x). \quad (6)$$

Endi (4) dan y bo'yicha hosila olamiz

$$u_y = -(1-2\beta)2^{1-2\beta}(-y)^{-2\beta} \int_0^1 Z(z) [t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt +$$

$$+ (-2y)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 Z'(z) [x-2t] [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt + \int_0^1 F'(z) [x-2t] [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt.$$

va (2) shartlarning ikkinchisidan foydalanamiz

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^{2\beta} u_y(x, y) = -(1-2\beta)2^{1-2\beta} Z(x) \int_0^1 [t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt =$$

$$= -(1-2\beta)2^{1-2\beta} Z(x) \frac{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)}{\Gamma(2-2\beta)} = v(x).$$

Bu yerdan

$$Z(x) = -2^{2\beta-1} \frac{\Gamma(1-2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)} v(x) \quad (7)$$

ekanligini topamiz.

Topilgan (6) va (7) larni (4) ga olib borib qo'yib, ko'rinishi o'zgartirilgan Koshi masalasining yechimini hosil qilamiz:

$$u(x, y) = \gamma_1 \int_0^1 \tau(x + y - 2yt)[t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt - \\ - \gamma_2 (-y)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 \nu(x + y - 2yt)[t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt, \quad (8)$$

bu yerda $\gamma_1 = \frac{\Gamma(2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(\beta)}$, $\gamma_2 = \frac{\Gamma(1-2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)}$.

Bevosita tekshirish yo'li bilan ishonch hosil qilish mumkinki, $\tau(t) \in C[0,1] \cap C^2(0,1)$ va $\nu(t) \in C^2(0,1)$ sinflardan va $\nu(t)$ funksiyada $t \rightarrow 0$ va $t \rightarrow 1$ da $1-2\beta$ dan oshmaydigan tartibda maxsuslikka intilishi mumkin bo'lsa, u holda $u(x, y)$ funksiya (8) formula bilan aniqlanadi va haqiqatan ham Ω sohada (1) tenglama uchun qo'yilgan ko'rinishi o'zgartirilgan Koshi masalasi yechimi bo'ladi.

Endi esa yuqoridagi nazariyamizni amaliyotda qo'llash jarayonini ko'rib chiqamiz.

(1) tenglamaning

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= x, \\ \lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^{2\beta} u_y(x, y) &= 3x - 1 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, y)$ yechimini toping.

Ma'lumki (1) tenglama uchun qo'yilgan ko'rinishi o'zgartirilgan Koshi masalasining yechimi (8) formula bilan berilgan edi. Shu formulaning $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalari o'rniga mos ravishda x va $3x-1$ larni qo'yib, kerakli integrallarni hisoblab, (1), (9) masala yechimining ko'rinishini topamiz.

$$u(x, y) = \gamma_1 \int_0^1 (x + y - 2yt)[t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt - \\ - \gamma_2 (-y)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 (3x + 3y - 6yt - 1)[t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt. \quad (10)$$

(10) tenglikdagi integrallarni hisoblaymiz va natijani chiqaramiz.

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x, y) &= \gamma_1(x+y) \int_0^1 [t(1-t)]^{\beta-1} dt - 2\gamma_1 y \int_0^1 t^\beta (1-t)^{\beta-1} dt - \\
 &- 3\gamma_2(x+y-1/3)(-y)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^1 [t(1-t)]^{-\beta} dt - 6\gamma_2(-y)^{2-2\beta} \int_0^1 t^{1-\beta} (1-t)^{-\beta} dt = \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\beta)\Gamma^2(\beta)}{\Gamma^2(\beta)\Gamma(2\beta)}(x+y) - 2 \frac{\Gamma(2\beta)\Gamma(1+\beta)\Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma^2(\beta)\Gamma(1+2\beta)} y - \\
 &- 3 \frac{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)\Gamma(1-2\beta)}{\Gamma(2-2\beta)\Gamma^2(1-\beta)}(x+y-1/3)(-y)^{1-2\beta} - \\
 &- 6 \frac{\Gamma(1-2\beta)\Gamma(2-\beta)\Gamma(1-\beta)}{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)\Gamma(3-2\beta)}(-y)^{2-2\beta} = x - \frac{3x-1}{1-2\beta}(-y)^{1-2\beta}
 \end{aligned}$$

Oxirgi ifoda esa (1), (9) masalaning yechimini beradi.

$$u(x, y) = x - \frac{3x-1}{1-2\beta}(-y)^{1-2\beta}$$

yechimni tekshirib ko'raylik:

1) x bo'yicha olingan ikkinchi tartibli xususiy hosila nolga teng, ya'ni $u_{xx} = 0$.

Endi y bo'yicha birinchi va ikkinchi tartibli hosilalarni hisoblaymiz:

$$u_y = (3x-1)(-y)^{-2\beta};$$

$$u_{yy} = 2\beta(3x-1)(-y)^{-1-2\beta}.$$

Bularni (1) tenglamaga qo'yamiz,

$$u_{xx} - u_{yy} - \frac{2\beta}{y}u_y = 0 - 2\beta(3x-1)(-y)^{-1-2\beta} - \frac{2\beta}{y}(3x-1)(-y)^{-2\beta} = 0.$$

Bulardan xulosa shuki, topilgan yechim berilgan tenglamani qanoatlantiradi.

2) $y=0$ da $u(x,0) = x$; $\lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^{2\beta} u_y = 3x-1$ bo'lib, bu esa berilgan

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiradi.

Demak, ushbu fikrlardan xulosa chiqarish mumkinki,

$$u(x, y) = x - \frac{3x-1}{1-2\beta}(-y)^{1-2\beta} \text{ funksiya (1), (9) masalaning yechimi ekan.}$$

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